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ABSTRACTS

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**Plasmid and its application in evolution of phytopathogenic bacteria
Xanthomonas citri pv. *viticola***

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Abstract: Globally grape production is severely threatened by bacterial leaf spot which is caused by *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* (*Xcv*). The disease has gained considerable importance due to climate change. Genome diversity and distribution of genes responsible for various factors in the pathogen are not well understood. Plasmids are likely to play an important role in maintaining pathogenicity and developing bacterial fitness in the field. The evolution of pathogenicity factors and horizontal gene transfer events mostly occur due to plasmid. Present study was conducted at ICAR-NRCG, Pune to study several plasmid-borne traits in *Xcv* collected from twenty-three different locations. Four different curing agents viz. ethidium bromide (EtBr), acridine orange (AO), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and elevated temperature were used to cure the plasmid. The results demonstrated no diversity amongst plasmid size (23kb) of isolates. Wide range of variation was observed in the efficacy of curing agent and was observed that plasmid curing had a major impact on characteristics like shape, pathogenicity, exopolysaccharide synthesis, and antibiotic sensitivity. Cured *Xcv* had shown variation with respect to the traits tested. Phenotypic characters like colour, size, shape, elevation, appearance and margin were affected by the curing of plasmid indicating that these traits are plasmid-borne. Moreover, exopolysaccharide production and pathogenicity were significantly reduced in the cured isolates. Antibiotic sensitivity was the crucial part of the study which suggested that most of the isolates had resistance trait on the plasmid. This study highlighted the importance of plasmids as vehicles for exchanging genetic elements between plant pathogenic bacteria and contributing to bacterial adaptation to the environment.

Keywords: Plasmid, curing, antibiotics, pathogenicity, exopolysaccharide production *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*.

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